

A New Synthesis of some naturally occurring Isocoumarins. 8-Hydroxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (Mellein) and 8-Hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin

JAWAHAR SINHA, RAMAYAN PRASAD SINGH and JAGDISH N. SRIVASTAVA*

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

Manuscript received 20 January 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

3-Methyl-8-methoxyisochroman (5a) on oxidation furnishes 3-methyl-8-methoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a), and demethylated with hydriodic acid to 3-methyl-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (mellein) (7a). Treatment of 6a with *N*-bromosuccinimide followed by refluxing with triethylamine furnishes 3-methyl-8-methoxyisocoumarin (8a) which on demethylation with hydriodic acid yields 3-methyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (9a). 5a and 3-methyl-6-methoxyisochroman (5b) obtained by treating 3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (4) with HCHO/HCl are separated by fractional distillation. 4 is obtained from *m*-methoxyphenylacetaldehyde (3) by Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium bromide. The aldehyde (3) is obtained from *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde (1) by Darzens glycidic ester condensation followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the resulting product.

A new route to the synthesis of 4-alkyl- and 3,4-dialkylisocoumarins has recently been reported^{1,2}.

Employing this route, *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde³ (1), obtained from *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, was converted into *m*-methoxyphenylacetaldehyde (3) via ethyl-β-(*m*-methoxy)phenylglycidate (2). The ester was obtained from 1 by Darzens glycidic ester condensation and was subsequently hydrolysed followed by decarboxylation to give 3, characterised as 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative. Treatment of the aldehyde (3) with methylmagnesium iodide furnished 3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (4). This alcohol was taken in formalin (37%) and dry dioxane mixture. Bubbling of hydrogen chloride gas through this solution at 55–60° afforded a mixture of 8-methoxy-3-methylisochroman (5a) and 6-methoxy-3-methylisochroman (5b) which were separated by fractional distillation under reduced pressure. Oxidation the isochroman (5a) by chromium trioxide in glacial acetic acid or by selenium dioxide in boiling xylene furnished 8-methoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a), m.p. 66–7° (lit.⁴ 67–8°). Demethylation of the isocoumarin (6a) with 87% hydriodic acid gave 8-hydroxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (mellein, 7a), m.p. 56–7°; while natural mellein⁵, a metabolite produced by *Aspergillus*, melts at 57–8°. The dihydrocoumarin (7a) responded to the ferric chloride test and exhibited a broad band at 3 400–3 200 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra showing intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the hydroxyl with the carbonyl of the lactone ring. The isocoumarin (6a) furnished 8-methoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (8a), on treatment with NBS in boiling carbon tetrachloride in presence of a 60 W lamp followed by refluxing the 4-bromo-derivative obtained after removal of the solvent with triethylamine for 2 h. Demethylation of the methyliso-

coumarin (8a) with hydriodic acid (87%) resulted in the formation of 8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (9a), m.p. 99–100°. Benz⁶ obtained the same compound, m.p. 100°, from the fungus *Marasmius yamealis*. The compound 9a was found to be a chelated phenol soluble in alkali and gave a blue violet ferric reaction.

Experimental

Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra (60 MHz) were recorded on a Varian A60 instrument with TMS as an internal standard.

Ethyl β-(m-methoxy)phenylglycidate (2): To a mixture of *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde³ (13.0 g) and dry ethyl chloroacetate (20.0 g) in dry benzene (50 ml), sodium ethoxide solution in ethanol (4.0 g sodium in 50 ml absolute ethanol) was added dropwise at 20°. After stirring the mixture for 2 h at room temperature, it was poured on crushed ice. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with benzene (3×50 ml). The organic layer and the benzene extracts were mixed, washed with water (3×50 ml) and dilute acetic acid (2.0 ml in 50 ml water) and then dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄). After removal of the solvent, the liquid residue was distilled under reduced pressure, (14 g), b.p. 98–99°/4.5 mm (Found: C, 64.62; H, 6.52. C₁₂H₁₄O₄ calcd for: C, 64.86; H, 6.30%); ν_{max} (neat) 3 040, 3 000, 2 910 (C–H), 1 730 (C=O of ester), 1 605, 1 585, 1 440 (Ar), 1 220 (epoxy) and 1 130 cm⁻¹ (methoxy).

m-Methoxyphenylacetaldehyde (3): Ethyl β-(*m*-methoxy)phenylglycidate (10.0 g) was added to a

Reagents: (i) $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COOEt}$, (ii) OEt^- , (iii) aqueous NaOH , (iv) Me_2MgBr , (v) HCHO/HCl , (vi) fractional distillation, (vii) CrO_3 or SeO_2 , (viii) HI , (ix) $\text{NBS-Et}_3\text{N}$, (x) HI .

stirred solution of sodium hydroxide (20.0 g) in water (40 ml) and stirring was continued for 2 h at 50–60° resulting in a clear homogeneous liquid which on cooling solidified, and acidified to congo red with hydrochloric acid (6 N), heated for 1 h on a water-bath with the evolution of carbon dioxide and finally separation of an oil. After cooling, the oil was extracted with benzene (2×20 ml), and the combined benzene extract washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave *m*-methoxyphenylacetaldehyde (4.0 g). Attempt to distil the oil resulted in the resinification of the aldehyde. It gave 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 118°d (Found: C, 80.10; H, 7.35. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 80.69; H, 7.46 %); ν_{max} (neat) 3 040, 2 990, 2 910, 1 720, 1 620, 1 605, 1 590 and 1 140 cm^{-1} .

3-(*m*-Methoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol (4): *m*-Methoxyphenylacetaldehyde (5 g) in dry ether (15 ml) was added to the Grignard solution, prepared from magnesium (2 g) and methyl iodide (10 g) in dry ether (20 ml), with stirring and was refluxed for 1 h. The ethereal solution was poured onto crushed ice, acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether (2×25 ml). The ether extract was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried (anhydrous K_2CO_3). The solvent was removed and the residue triturated with petroleum ether and crystallised from ethyl acetate–petroleum

ether to afford 3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-ol, m.p. 58° (Found: C, 72.46; H, 8.14. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 72.28; H, 8.43%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 440 (OH), 3 025, 2 990, 2 940, 2 900, 2 880 (C–H), 1 605, 1 590 (Ar), 1 460, 1 390 and 1 105 cm^{-1} (methoxy).

6-Methoxy-3-methylisochroman (5b) and 8-methoxy-3-methylisochroman (5a): Dry hydrogen chloride gas was bubbled in a solution of 4 (5 g), formalin (5 ml), concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml) and dry dioxane (10 ml) for 2 h at such a rate that the temperature of the mixture remained in the range 50–60°. After cooling, it was poured into ice-water and extracted with ether (3×25 ml). The ether extract was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and water, and dried (fused CaCl_2). After removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish two fractions.

Fraction I was identified as 6-methoxy-3-methylisochroman, (1.6 g), b.p. 138°/1 mm (Found: C, 81.80; H, 8.92. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 81.48; H, 8.64%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 245 and 280 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 3 010, 2 900, 1 430, 1 390 (C–H), 1 110, 1 090 (ethereal) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ (CCl_4) 1.33 (3H, d, C_8-CH_3), 2.7 (1H, m, H-3), 3.55 (2H, d, H-4), 4.35 (2H, s, H-1), 3.50 (3H, s, C_6-OCH_3) and 8.10 (3H, m, Ar). Fraction II was identified as 8-methoxy-3-methylisochroman (0.6 g), b.p. 154°/1 mm (Found: C, 81.86; H, 8.80. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 81.48; H, 8.64%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 250 and 278 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 2 990, 2 910, 1 420, 1 400 (C–H), 1 120, 1 095 (ethereal) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ (CCl_4) 1.32 (3H, d, C_8-CH_3), 2.70 (1H, m, H-3), 3.60 (2H, d, H-4), 4.60 (2H, s, H-1), 3.70 (3H, s, C_8-OCH) and 7.9 (3H, m, Ar).

8-Methoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a): (i) A solution of chromium trioxide (3.0 g) in water (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added with stirring to 8-methoxy-3-methylisochroman (1.0 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) at room temperature. The reaction was exothermic and it was cooled occasionally by ice to maintain the temperature at 30–5°. It was stirred for 2 h at room temperature, then mixed with an equal volume of water and was extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (10%) and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave a gummy solid which was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to afford 8-methoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.5 g) as prisms, m.p. 66–7° (lit. 67–8°; synthesised earlier by a different route) (Found: C, 75.60; H, 7.12. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 75.0, H, 6.81%). (ii) A solution of 5a (1.0 g) in xylene (15 ml) was treated with freshly prepared selenium dioxide (1.5 g) and refluxed for 6 h. The hot reaction mixture was filtered and the gummy residue obtained after removal of the solvent was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g), eluting the column with the same solvent. After removal of the solvent, a solid gum was obtained which was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p.

40–60°) to afford 8-methoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.5 g) as prisms, m.p. 66–7°. M.m.p. of the specimen obtained by methods (i) and (ii) showed no depression, thus identical with the specimen obtained in Method I; $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 240 and 280 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 100, 2 900, 1 455, 1 405, (C–H), 1 730 (C=O of lactone), 1 110 (ethereal) and 1 590 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ (CCl_4) 3.98 (3H, s, C_8 – OCH_3), 1.45 (3H, d, C_3 – CH_3), 4.40 (1H, m, H-3), 4.30 (2H, d, H-4) and 7.20 (3H, m, Ar).

8-Hydroxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (mellein) (7a): A mixture of **6a** (0.2 g) and freshly distilled hydriodic acid (5 ml, 57%) was refluxed for 3 h. After removal of hydriodic acid, it was cooled, extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residue crystallised from ethyl acetate–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to afford 8-hydroxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.12 g) as needles, m.p. 57–8° (naturally occurring mellein melting at 56–7°) (Found: C, 68.25; H, 5.82. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 67.41; H, 5.61%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 235, 285 and 320 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 250–3 400 (OH), 2 990, 2 900, 1 450, 1 380 and 1 600 cm^{-1} (Ar).

8-Methoxy-3-methylisocoumarin (8a): A mixture of 8-methoxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.2 g), *N*-bromosuccinimide (1.0 g), benzoyl peroxide (0.2 g) in dry carbon tetrachloride (40 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, the reaction flask being kept close to a 60 W lamp. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the filtrate washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent on a water-bath, the residue was refluxed with triethylamine (25 ml) for 8 h and the gummy residue left after removal of triethylamine was triturated repeatedly with ice-cold hydrochloric acid (2 *N*) followed by water. It was

then taken in petroleum ether, washed again with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residual oil solidified on long standing, and then crystallised from *n*-hexane as colourless needles (0.12 g), m.p. 107–8° (Found: C, 70.25; H, 6.05. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 69.47, H, 5.26%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 275 and 315 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 000, 2 910, 1 735, 1 620, 1 610, 1 560, 1 400 and 1 110 cm^{-1} (ethereal); δ (CCl_4) 2.5 (3H, s, C_8 – CH_3), 2.7 (3H, s, C_4 – CH_3), 4.2 (3H, s, C_8 – OCH_3), 7.9 (1H, m, H-7) and 7.3 (2H, m, Ar).

8-Hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (9a): A mixture of **8a** (0.1 g) and freshly distilled hydriodic acid (3 ml, 57%) was refluxed for 2 h. After removal of the hydriodic acid, it was cooled, extracted with ether, washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the solid residue crystallised from ethyl acetate to give 8-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (0.06 g), m.p. 97–8° (elaborated by the fungus *Marasmius yamealis*⁶, m.p. 99–100°) (Found: C, 68.72; H, 5.14. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ calcd. for: C, 68.18; H, 4.54%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 255 and 320 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 200–3 400 (OH), 2 980, 2 900, 1 740, 1 610, 1 590, 1 420 and 1 400 cm^{-1} .

References

1. R. P. SINGH and J. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 104.
2. R. P. SINGH and J. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 964.
3. A. JENKINS, *Org. Synth.*, **1**, 387.
4. J. BLAIN and G. T. NEWBOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2871.
5. T. YABUTA and Y. J. SUMIKY, *Agric. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1934, **10**, 723.
6. G. BENZ, *Ark. Kems. Min. Geol.*, 1959, **14**, 511.